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Title: Shades of Green: Unveiling Community Engagement in Barangay Greening Program

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Abstract

This study examined community engagement in the Barangay Greening Program, addressing the gap in understanding how demographic factors influence participation in grassroots environmental initiatives. It aims to explore residents' attitudes, perceptions, and levels of involvement while identifying key factors that affect engagement. Qualitative and quantitative approaches were used, combining surveys, interviews, and observations to gather data. Findings reveal that while community awareness of the program is high, active participation remains limited. Middle-aged individuals, females, and those with higher educational attainment and socio-economic status show greater involvement, particularly in leadership and planning roles. In contrast, younger and lower-income individuals exhibit minimal engagement. Statistical analysis indicates significant differences in community participation based on age and education, with education and economic status emerging as the strongest predictors of involvement. The study also highlighted key factors that influence engagement, including awareness and education, socio-economic conditions, community leadership, past experiences with environmental disasters, and perceived incentives. Based on these findings, the study recommends targeted interventions such as age and gender responsive programs, leadership trainings, incentive-driven activities, and expanded environmental education campaigns. Strengthening these areas can bridge the gap between awareness and action, fostering active participation. Ultimately, the study provides valuable insights for policymakers, environmental advocates, and local leaders in crafting more inclusive and effective strategies to sustain grassroots environmental efforts and build community resilience against climate change.

Keywords: Climate change, environmental stewardship, environmental sustainability, green initiatives

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Introduction

Environmental issues and the ability of humanity to live sustainably within planetary boundaries have become paramount concerns globally (Leonardsson & Habyarimana, 2022). In the face of escalating climate change concerns, communities worldwide are increasingly embracing proactive measures to combat its adverse impacts. Didi van Doren et al. (2020) affirmed that local governments, in particular, play a prominent role in experimentation for sustainability transitions and have shown farsighted leadership in addressing climate change and fostering sustainability. By responding to imminent societal needs, local initiatives can trigger adaptive responses to crises and thus also provoke changes to the system as a whole (Castro-Acre & Vanclay, 2020). Among these initiatives, the Barangay Greening Program stands out as a localized effort aimed at fostering environmental sustainability at the grassroots level. This research embarks upon a comprehensive examination of community engagement within the framework of this program, with the aim of elucidating the depth of residents' comprehension and involvement in greening endeavors.

The urgency of addressing climate change has underscored the importance of community-driven initiatives (Atwoli et al., 2022; Atwoli et al., 2021; Campbell et al., 2018; Gills & Morgan, 2020). Localized programs like the Barangay Greening Program are pivotal in mobilizing collective action and fostering a sense of environmental stewardship among residents. There has been increasing attention to and investment in local environmental stewardship in conservation and environmental management policies and programs globally. However, environmental stewardship has not received adequate conceptual attention (Bennett et al., 2018). Hence, understanding the dynamics of community engagement within such initiatives is crucial for devising effective strategies to mitigate climate change and promote sustainable development. The global scale of many current environmental issues might lead to the perception that local actions can no longer meet these challenges. However, one way through which people get involved in promoting sustainability and in responding to external drivers of change, using their expertise and knowledge, is by engaging in local environmental stewardship actions and initiatives (Bennett et al., 2018).

On February 24, 2011, President Benigno S. Aquino III issued Executive Order (EO) 26, declaring the implementation of the National Greening Program as a government priority program to reduce poverty, promote food security, environmental stability and biodiversity conservation, and enhance climate change mitigation and adaptation. It is, therefore, not a straightforward reforestation effort but a larger program intended to attain other important national objectives as well (EO, 2011). This greening program is cascaded in the local government for more efficient implementation and monitoring. Hence, the Barangay Greening Program.

The primary objective of this research is to delve into the complexities of community involvement in greening efforts within the barangay setting. By employing a qualitative-quantitative approach that integrates surveys, interviews, and observational data, this study sought to provide a nuanced understanding of the factors influencing community engagement in the greening program.

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The significance of community engagement in environmental initiatives cannot be overstated. It is not merely about the number of trees planted or waste recycled but about instilling a sense of ownership and responsibility among residents towards their local environment. Effective community engagement fosters a culture of environmental consciousness, which is essential for the long-term success of sustainability initiatives. Public participation in climate change adaptation initiatives enhances the capacity to cope with climate change risks (Hugel & Davies, 2020; IPCC, 2018).

This research aimed to contribute to the existing body of knowledge by shedding light on the intricacies of community involvement in environmental programs at the grassroots level. By examining community attitudes, behaviors, and participatory activities, it seeks to uncover underlying motivations, barriers, and facilitators of engagement within the Barangay Greening Program.

The outcomes of this investigation hold significant implications for various stakeholders, including policymakers, environmental advocates, and community leaders. Insights gleaned from this study can inform the formulation of strategies to enhance community participation and comprehension of eco-friendly practices. By understanding the factors that drive or impede community engagement, stakeholders can effectively tailor interventions to promote environmental stewardship within the barangay.

Furthermore, this research endeavored to facilitate the development of targeted interventions and propositions for a more robust and efficacious greening campaign. By identifying gaps and areas for improvement, it sought to enhance the effectiveness and sustainability of the Barangay Greening Program, ultimately contributing to the broader goal of building resilient and environmentally sustainable communities.

In essence, this scholarly inquiry aimed to illuminate the subtleties of community engagement in environmental initiatives within the barangay context. By providing insights into the dynamics of community involvement, it seeks to catalyze the advancement of sustainable practices and fortify the resilience of communities amidst the formidable challenges posed by climate change. Through rigorous analysis and interpretation, this study aimed to offer actionable insights that can drive positive change and contribute to the collective effort toward a greener and more sustainable future for all.

Review of Related Literature and Studies

Community Engagement in Environmental Initiatives

Community participation in local government's environmental initiatives is essential for ensuring the effectiveness and sustainability of such projects. Empirical studies in various parts of the world have investigated the nature of this participation, the factors that influence it, and its impact on environmental outcomes.

According to Hugel and Davies (2020), community engagement is widely recognized as a critical component of successful environmental initiatives. The need for public participation has featured prominently in calls for climate action. Even earlier studies, such as those by Reed (2008), have emphasized the importance of involving residents in decision-making processes, project planning, and implementation to ensure the sustainability and effectiveness of environmental programs. Reed (2008) further argues that meaningful

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engagement fosters a sense of ownership and responsibility among community members, leading to greater support and participation in sustainability initiatives. Therefore, the complex and dynamic nature of environmental issues necessitates community engagement in crafting national and local policies.

Meers et al. (2019) highlight that engaging the community in responding to the adverse effects of climate change encourages collaboration. Governments actively encourage citizens' initiatives for climate action to enhance the resilience of communities to climate change. This increased responsabilization of citizens has implications for the roles of governments, as noted by Jackson (2018). While the degree of government involvement may not necessarily decline, government roles may need to shift towards a more collaborative and responsive approach, enabling and facilitating community initiatives that are self-governed by citizens.

Fonataba et al. (2018) evaluate the level of community participation in the management of a nature tourism park in Sorong City, identifying the roles played by the community and the challenges faced in engagement. Additionally, Nugraheni and Suyatna (2020) examine the active role of community participation in dealing with flood disasters in several regions in Indonesia. They analyze various forms of participation, such as financial contributions, labor, education, and infrastructure development supervision.

These sources collectively analyze various aspects of community participation, including the level of involvement, the types of engagement, and the outcomes of such participation in environmental management. They offer valuable insights into how community members can effectively participate in and influence local government environmental programs.

Barangay Greening Programs

Greening programs refer to initiatives aimed at promoting environmental sustainability, conservation, and the adoption of eco-friendly practices. The Barangay Greening Program, as part of the National Greening Program, represents a crucial avenue for promoting environmental sustainability at the grassroots level. These localized initiatives seek to enhance the ecological health and resilience of communities by undertaking activities such as tree planting, implementing waste management practices, and promoting sustainable land use.

While research specifically focused on barangay greening programs is limited, studies on similar community-based environmental initiatives offer valuable insights into the challenges and opportunities associated with such endeavors.

Zabala et al. (2018) discuss the development needs of Barangay Tanawan, including beautification, sanitation, and the promotion of Garden Tourism. Paz et al. (2020) focus on improving solid waste management, a critical component of greening initiatives, through behavioral change and alternative disposal plans. Additionally, Monocay and Mejica (2020) examine how governance at the barangay level can engage in environmental and greening initiatives as part of their performance frameworks. Lessons in sustainable development governance from Blanco (2020) might inform future green initiatives in barangays, including land banking and the revitalization of industries related to greening efforts.

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These references collectively explore themes of development, beautification, tourism, waste management, and governance, all of which are essential elements of greening initiatives at the community level.

Factors Influencing Community Engagement

Several factors influence community engagement in environmental initiatives, including socioeconomic status, education level, cultural beliefs, and perceived benefits and costs of participation (Pretty, 2003; Stern, 2002). Research by Stern (2002) suggests that individuals with higher levels of education and income are more likely to engage in pro-environmental behaviors due to their greater awareness and access to resources.

Xiaomei (2023) reports on current environmental initiatives and citizen participation measures in China, highlighting the trickle-down effect on local government based on commitments to short- and long-term strategies aimed at protecting the environment through eco-security and improving cooperation among different levels of society. This study aims to explore local government actions following these commitments, the theoretical system and governance model of environmental initiatives and citizen participation in China, and the influencing factors of such initiatives and participation.

Hussain et al. (2022) demonstrate that government support and organizational innovativeness significantly impact community participation and project success. Furthermore, community participation partially mediates these relationships. The findings are expected to provide guidelines for government authorities to enhance policies for involving the community as a mediator in project planning and decision-making for renewable energy projects. Alam's (2013) study also emphasizes the importance of understanding public support in implementing government projects related to environmental sustainability. The socio-demographic profile of residents and their perceptual characteristics positively correlate with their willingness to participate.

The Theoretical Framework

The Social Ecological Model (SEM) serves as the foundational framework for understanding the complex interplay of individual, interpersonal, organizational, community, and societal factors that shape human behavior within the context of environmental initiatives (McLeroy et al., 1988). At the individual level, factors such as knowledge, attitudes, beliefs, and perceptions influence residents' decision-making and participation in greening activities. Interpersonal relationships, social networks, and communication channels mediate the diffusion of information, social norms, and peer influences within the community. Organizational structures, leadership, and community resources play a crucial role in facilitating or constraining residents' engagement in the greening program. Community characteristics, including socio-economic status, cultural values, and institutional arrangements, shape the context within which environmental initiatives are implemented. Finally, broader societal factors, such as policy frameworks, economic incentives, and cultural norms, influence the overall sustainability of community-based environmental efforts. This framework guides the research in examining the multi-

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dimensional factors influencing residents' participation in greening activities. It offers theoretical foundations for interpreting the findings and informing the development of effective strategies for promoting environmental stewardship within barangays.

Figure 1

The Social Ecological Model (McKee et al., 2002)

Conceptual and Analytical Framework

Conceptual Framework

This study sought to elucidate the complex interplay between demographic factors and community engagement in the Barangay Greening program. By examining these relationships and their implications for policy-making, the study aims to contribute to the development of more inclusive, effective, and sustainable greening initiatives at the barangay level.

At the individual level, demographic factors such as age, socioeconomic status, and educational attainment play crucial roles in shaping individuals' attitudes, behaviors, and levels of participation in community programs. Younger residents may exhibit higher levels of enthusiasm and energy for environmental initiatives, while older residents may bring wisdom and experience to the table. Socioeconomic status can influence access to resources and opportunities for engagement, with higher-income individuals potentially having greater capacity to participate actively. Educational attainment, meanwhile, may correlate with awareness and understanding of environmental issues, as well as the ability to evaluate and contribute to greening efforts critically.

Interpersonal dynamics within the community also come into play, as social networks, relationships, and community norms influence individuals' decision-making processes. Residents may be more likely to engage in greening activities if they perceive

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social support from their peers, neighbors, and community leaders. Conversely, social barriers such as lack of trust, conflicts of interest, or competing priorities may hinder participation.

At the community level, understanding the demographic composition of residents and their levels of participation in the Barangay Greening program can provide valuable insights into the overall effectiveness and inclusivity of greening initiatives. By examining demographic differences in participation rates, policymakers can identify marginalized or underserved groups and develop targeted interventions to enhance their engagement. For example, if certain age groups or socio-economic strata are found to have lower participation rates, initiatives such as tailored outreach campaigns, incentive programs, or educational workshops may be implemented to encourage greater involvement.

Furthermore, exploring the correlations between demographic factors and participation levels can uncover underlying patterns and relationships that inform policy decisions. For instance, if higher educational attainment is found to be positively correlated with greater participation in greening activities, policymakers may prioritize investments in environmental education and awareness-raising programs. Similarly, if socioeconomic disparities are identified as barriers to participation, policies aimed at promoting equitable access to resources and opportunities may be recommended.

Figure 2
Conceptual Framework

Analytical Framework

The demographic variables of interest included age, socio-economic status (SES), and educational attainment. Age was categorized into different groups to explore potential

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differences in participation levels across various life stages. Socioeconomic status was measured using indicators such as household income. Educational attainment was assessed based on the highest level of formal education completed by respondents.

Statement of the Problem

This study sought to unveil the extent of community engagement in the Barangay Greening Program. Specifically, it answers the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - a. Age,
 - b. Gender;
 - c. Socio-economic status; and
 - d. Educational attainment?
2. What are the prevailing attitudes and perceptions of the community towards environmental sustainability and the Barangay Greening Program?
3. What is the extent of community engagement of the respondents when they are grouped according to their demographic profiles?
4. Is there a significant difference in the extent of community engagement when the respondents are grouped according to their demographic profiles?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of community engagement and the respondents' profiles?
6. What are the factors that contribute to community engagement in the barangay greening program?

Null Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in the extent of community engagement when the respondents are grouped according to their demographic profiles.
2. There is no significant correlation between the extent of community engagement and the respondents' profiles.

Methodology

This study employed a qualitative-quantitative approach to unveil the extent of community engagement in the Barangay Greening Program and address the research questions posed.

Design

This study adopted both quantitative and qualitative methods to explore community engagement in the Barangay Greening Program from multiple perspectives. This comprehensive approach enhanced the rigor and comprehensiveness of the study, enabling a nuanced understanding of the phenomenon under investigation.

The quantitative component involves the use of surveys to collect structured data from a representative sample of respondents within the barangay community. The surveys will gather demographic information, attitudes, and perceptions toward environmental

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sustainability and the Barangay Greening Program. This component allows for the systematic collection of numerical data, enabling statistical analysis to examine relationships, differences, and patterns across demographic groups.

The qualitative component entails conducting semi-structured interviews with a subset of participants to explore their experiences, motivations, and barriers related to community engagement in the Barangay Greening Program. Through open-ended questions and probing, this component seeks to capture rich, in-depth insights into participants' perspectives, providing a deeper understanding of the phenomenon under study. This also includes a narrative of the researchers' observations regarding the implementation of the greening program.

Locale

The study was conducted at Barangay District IV, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. This barangay, formerly known as *Poblacion*, has a population of 3,670, comprising 5.42% of the population of Bayombong. It has approximately 942 households, and approximately 57% of its population belongs to the age group 18 and above (PhilAtlas, 2020).

District IV has existing greening programs, which include tree planting, gardening, solid waste management, banning of styrofoam, prohibition of burning plastics, "tapat ko, lines ko," and others. These barangay greening initiatives will be the subject of investigation in this study.

Participants and Sampling

The study encompassed residents aged 18 and above from the barangay, with one representative per household to reflect the diversity of households in the area. Additionally, the qualitative phase involved community leaders, program coordinators, and other stakeholders engaged in environmental initiatives within the barangay.

A stratified random sampling approach was adopted to ensure comprehensive representation across various demographic segments within the barangay. Stratification will be based on key socio-demographic factors, including age, gender, education level, and socio-economic status, thereby capturing the breadth of community diversity.

The sample size will be determined using the Raosoft sample size calculator. There are 942 households in the barangay, with 304 respondents.

Research Instrument

The research instrument for this study consisted of a combination of quantitative and qualitative tools designed to collect data on residents' extent of community engagement in the Barangay Greening Program. The research instrument included a survey questionnaire to collect data from residents within the barangay. It included closed-ended and Likert-scale items that assessed the respondent's profile and extent of engagement in the barangay greening program.

A semi-structured interview guide was used to facilitate in-depth qualitative interviews with residents, community leaders, program coordinators, and other stakeholders. The interview guide included open-ended questions and explored

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participants' perspectives, experiences, motivations, and suggestions related to community engagement in the Barangay Greening Program. Questions were designed to elicit rich qualitative data that allowed nuanced insights into the factors influencing residents' participation and the contextual dynamics of community involvement.

Data Gathering Procedure

Data collection commenced upon securing approval from the Research Council via endorsement from the University Research Center. The research tool has undergone validation. Following validation and approval, the research instrument was distributed to the potential respondents. Additionally, permission for questionnaire distribution, retrieval, and interviews was sought from the barangay captain of District IV.

Treatment of Data

Descriptive statistics was used in the analysis of the respondents' demographic profiles. Responses to survey items assessing attitudes and perceptions were analyzed thematically to identify recurring themes, patterns, and variations in community perspectives. Qualitative coding techniques were employed to categorize responses and uncover nuanced insights into prevailing attitudes towards environmental sustainability and the Barangay Greening Program. Quantitative measures of community engagement, such as participation rates and frequency of involvement in greening activities, were analyzed across different demographic profiles. Inferential statistics, such as t-tests or ANOVA, were used to compare engagement levels between demographic groups, providing insights into variations in participation based on age, gender, socio-economic status, and educational attainment. Statistical tests, including analysis of variance (ANOVA) or chi-square tests, were conducted to determine if there are significant differences in the extent of community engagement when respondents are grouped according to their demographic profiles. Correlation analysis, such as Pearson's correlation coefficient, was used to examine the relationship between the extent of community engagement and respondents' demographic profiles. This analysis assessed the strength and direction of associations between variables, providing insights into how demographic factors influence community engagement in the Barangay Greening Program.

Ethical Considerations

This research was submitted to the Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Board (SMUREB) for review and approval. SMUREB has the following address and contact information:

- Email: reb@smu.edu.ph
- Mobile Number: 091771053041
- Office Address: 2F Rev. John Van Bauwel Hall, SMU main Campus, Ponce St., Don Mariano Marcos, 3700 Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines

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To uphold ethical standards throughout this research endeavor, the researchers adhered strictly to the following principles:

a. *Conflict of Interest*: The researchers maintained a singular focus on the intended purpose of the study, which is primarily for educational purposes, and did not extend beyond it.

b. *Confidentiality and Data Protection*: Ensuring the privacy of respondents and safeguarding the confidentiality of data is paramount. Therefore, the researchers refrained from disclosing the identities of respondents at any stage of the research. Instead, anonymized codes were utilized. The data collected was utilized exclusively for the research study and was securely disposed of upon completion. Both paper-based and electronic data were securely stored, with access restricted solely to the researchers.

c. *Management of Vulnerability*: Respondents were not exposed to any form of harm in order to participate in the research survey. Participation was entirely voluntary, and respondents retained the right to withdraw from the study at any point. Participants who experienced discomfort during the research process were provided with the necessary assistance.

d. *Informed Consent*: Prior to the commencement of the study, informed consent was thoroughly explained to the respondents and subsequently administered to them.

e. *Risks of the Study*: Participation in the study carried no inherent risks for the participants.

f. *Benefits of the Study*: Engagement in the study will contribute to the enhancement of the barangay greening program. The findings will serve as a foundation for barangay policymakers to formulate policies concerning environmental sustainability, thereby benefiting both the current community and future generations.

g. *Terms of Reference*: The American Psychological Association (APA) 7th edition guidelines will be adhered to for citation and proper sourcing of materials utilized in the study. Findings were disseminated in a research forum and will be shared in the barangay. Likewise, the study may be submitted for publication in a refereed journal.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the findings of the study on the extent of community engagement in the Barangay Greening Program. The results highlight the level of participation among community members and the challenges encountered in sustaining environmental efforts. Through data analysis, key trends and insights are discussed, providing a clearer understanding of the community's role in promoting environmental sustainability. The discussion further explores the implications of these findings for future policy-making and program enhancement.

Profile of the Respondents

A. Age

The age distribution of respondents in the study reveals that the majority fall within the middle-aged group (36-55 years old), comprising 53.7% of the total participants. Specifically, the 46-55 age group represents the largest portion (28.0%), followed by the 36-45 age group (25.7%). Meanwhile, the younger age groups (18-25 and 26-35) each account for 18.8%, and the senior group (56 and above) constitutes only 8.9%. This can be gleaned from the table below.

Table 1
Profile of the Respondents Based on Age

	Frequency	Percent
18-25	57	18.8
26-35	57	18.8
36-45	78	25.7
46-55	85	28.0
56 above	27	8.9
Total	304	100.0

B. Gender

The data indicates that the majority of respondents in the Barangay Greening Program are female (65.8%), while male participants make up 34.2% of the total sample. The table below shows this.

Table 2
Profile of the Respondents Based on Gender

	Frequency	Percent
Male	104	34.2
Female	200	65.8
Total	304	100.0

C. Educational Attainment

The data, which can be gleaned from the table below, reveal that the majority of respondents have attained at least some level of college education, with 30.9% at the college level and 26.6% being college graduates. In contrast, those with only elementary education (level and graduate) account for a small percentage (7.5%), while high school-level and high school graduates make up 34.8%. Notably, no respondents have pursued graduate studies or reported having no formal education.

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Table 3

Profile of the Respondents Based on Educational Attainment

	Frequency	Percent
elementary level	12	3.9
elementary graduate	11	3.6
high school level	56	18.4
high school graduate	50	16.4
college level	94	30.9
College Graduate	81	26.6
graduate studies	0	0
did not attend school	0	0
Total	304	100.0

D. Income/Economic Status

It can be gleaned from the data that the majority of respondents belong to low-income households, with 78.6% earning ₱10,000 or below per month. A smaller portion, 18.4%, falls within the ₱10,001–₱20,000 range, while only 3.0% of respondents have a monthly family income exceeding ₱20,000. Notably, no respondents reported earning above ₱40,000 per month.

Table 4

Profile of the Respondents Based on Income/Economic Status

	Frequency	Percent
10,000 and below	239	78.6
10001-20000	56	18.4
20001-30000	6	2.0
30001-40000	3	1.0
40001-50000	0	0.0
50001 and above	0	0.0
Total	304	100.0

The prevailing attitudes and perceptions towards the Barangay Greening Program

Attitudes of the respondents refer to their beliefs and values about environmental sustainability. Their perceptions connote how they view and engage with the program.

Table 5
The Respondents' Attitudes and Perceptions Towards the Greening Program

Statements	Mean	Standard Deviation
I participate in tree-planting events organized by the barangay.	2.99	0.86
I volunteer my time to maintain green spaces and public gardens in the barangay.	2.48	0.94
I attend educational workshops or seminars related to environmental conservation.	2.67	1.06
I participate in community clean-up drives to help improve the environment.	2.97	1.23
I take on a leadership role within the greening initiatives such as coordinating events or leading volunteer groups.	2.53	0.99
I donate resources to support greening initiatives.	3.51	0.81
I engage in advocacy efforts to promote environmental awareness and greening initiatives within my community.	2.81	1.09
I initiate or lead my own greening projects independently of organized initiatives.	2.72	1.01
I participate in regular meetings or discussions to provide input or feedback on the direction of the greening initiatives.	2.86	1.12
I collaborate with local schools or youth groups to promote environmental education and involvement in greening initiatives.	2.91	1.09
I do not use Styrofoam products.	3.27	1.03
I do not burn plastics.	3.28	1.09
I segregate my wastes for collection by the barangay solid waste management team.	3.25	0.97
I follow the "tapat ko, linis ko" program.	3.12	1.20
I participate in fundraising events or campaigns to support the ongoing activities of the greening program.	2.83	1.06
I regularly engage in outreach activities to encourage more community members to get involved in greening initiatives.	2.54	1.01

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I collaborate with local businesses or government agencies to secure resources or support for greening projects.	2.33	0.99
I advocate for policy changes or improvements at the local or regional level to promote environmental sustainability and support greening initiatives.	2.86	1.10
I mentor or support newcomers to the community who are interested in getting involved in greening initiatives.	2.70	1.07
I actively participate in monitoring and evaluation activities to assess the effectiveness and impact of greening initiatives.	2.43	0.96
Overall	2.85	0.64

In terms of the respondents' attitude towards environmental conservation, the data indicate that the community recognizes the importance of sustainability. The data suggest that respondents understand the harmful effects of non-biodegradable waste and are conscious of their environmental footprint. This is shown in the respondents' high score in avoiding the use of Styrofoam products and avoiding the burning of plastics. The data also reflect the respondents' belief that waste management and cleanliness contribute to a healthier environment as manifested in their high scores in segregating waste and following the "tapat ko, linis ko" program. Further, the data indicate the respondents' willingness to support environmental causes financially or materially, showing that respondents value sustainability but may prefer indirect participation. This observation aligns with the concept of the "value-action gap," which describes the discrepancy between individuals' professed values and their actual behaviors (Kollmuss & Agyeman, 2002). Barriers such as personal, social, and structural constraints often impede the translation of environmental concern into proactive action.

It can be inferred that while the community values environmental sustainability and recognizes the importance of greening initiatives, there is a preference for less physically demanding contributions, such as financial or material donations or passive waste management. Research has shown that passive involvement, such as responding to surveys or public announcements, is common in public participation. However, active engagement, which includes taking ownership of environmental processes, is less prevalent (Reed, 2008). This distinction is crucial, as active participation is often necessary for the long-term success of environmental programs.

In terms of the respondents' perceptions, the data reveal that while respondents see the value of the program, they do not strongly perceive themselves as key contributors. This can be inferred from their low participation in leadership roles and volunteerism. The respondents also manifested low engagement in monitoring and evaluation, indicating that community members do not view assessment and feedback as essential responsibilities, which may affect the program's long-term success. Studies have found that individuals who engage actively with green spaces report higher quality of life and better overall mood compared to those who engage passively (Wood et al., 2018). This suggests that fostering

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active participation in environmental initiatives could not only benefit the environment but also enhance individual well-being.

The prevailing attitudes show that the community values environmental sustainability but prefers passive engagement over active leadership. Meanwhile, perceptions indicate that respondents see the program as primarily barangay-driven rather than a shared responsibility requiring independent community action. Encouraging a shift from passive to active participation may be essential for the enduring success of environmental programs.

The respondents' extent of community engagement

The respondents' extent of community engagement can also be gleaned from Table 5. The overall mean score of 2.85 suggests that community engagement in the Barangay Greening Program is moderate. While respondents demonstrate awareness and participation in specific environmental activities, their engagement level varies depending on the type of initiative. Areas of strong engagement include donating resources to support greening initiatives (3.51), avoiding the use of Styrofoam products (3.27), not burning plastics (3.28), waste segregation (3.25), and following the "Tapat Ko, Linis Ko" program (3.12). This implies that the community prefers passive engagement, such as financial donations and compliance with waste management policies, rather than direct involvement in physically demanding activities.

Areas of moderate engagement include tree planting (2.99), clean-up drives (2.97), attending educational workshops (2.67), advocacy efforts (2.81), independent greening projects (2.72), participation in meetings and policy advocacy (2.86), and collaboration with schools or youth groups (2.91). These activities suggest occasional participation from the respondents.

Areas of weak engagement include volunteering to maintain green spaces (2.48), taking on leadership roles (2.53), engaging in outreach activities (2.54), monitoring and evaluation participation (2.43), and collaboration with businesses or government agencies (2.33). These activities reflect lower levels of involvement, particularly in leadership, long-term commitment, and collaboration.

Recent local studies reinforce these findings. For instance, a study assessing the National Greening Program (NGP) in Barangay San Antonio, Biri, Northern Samar, found that while there was community involvement in mangrove reforestation, the level of participation varied among different groups. The study highlighted the need for increased active engagement from community members to enhance the program's effectiveness (Saludario & Ogoc, 2022). Furthermore, a qualitative study conducted in Acmac, Iligan City, explored community-led initiatives for local environmental protection. The research delved into the motivations, strategies, challenges, and outcomes of such initiatives, shedding light on their transformative potential. It emphasized the importance of empowering local communities to take active roles in environmental programs to achieve sustainable outcomes (Eslit, 2023).

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These studies suggest that while there is an awareness and willingness to participate in environmental initiatives among Filipino communities, the depth of engagement often remains limited. Enhancing active participation, particularly in leadership roles and collaborative efforts, is crucial for the long-term success of programs like the Barangay Greening Program.

Difference in the extent of community engagement in terms of the profile variables

Age

Table 6

Difference in the Extent of Community Engagement when Respondents are Grouped According to Age

AGE	Mean	f	Std. Deviation	F	P-value
18-25	2.82 ^A	57	0.84	5.442***	0.001
26-35	2.71 ^A	57	0.67		
36-45	2.96 ^A	78	0.59		
46-55	3.00 ^A	85	0.49		
56 above	2.45 ^B	27	0.39		

*** significant at $\alpha=0.001$; Mean groups who do not share a common letter are significantly different from each other.

The analysis of variance (ANOVA) results indicate a statistically significant difference in community engagement levels across various age groups in the Barangay Greening Program ($F = 5.442, p = 0.001$). Specifically, respondents aged 46-55 ($M = 3.00$) and 36-45 ($M = 2.96$) exhibit the highest engagement levels, suggesting that individuals in these age brackets may have more stable routines, a heightened sense of community responsibility, and the physical capability to participate in greening initiatives. Conversely, younger adults aged 18-25 ($M = 2.82$) and 26-35 ($M = 2.71$) demonstrate moderate engagement, potentially due to busy schedules related to education, work, or career development, which may limit their participation in community activities. This is similar to the findings of Goldman, D., Pe'er, S., & Yavetz, B. (2019). The lowest engagement is observed among those aged 56 and above ($M = 2.45$), possibly due to physical limitations, health concerns, or a preference for less labor-intensive roles.

These findings align with previous research on age-related differences in environmental engagement. For instance, Aspe et al. (2017) found that younger individuals aged 15-25 in a local Philippine city exhibited the highest positive perceptions of urban forestry initiatives. The study suggested that this age group, primarily composed of students, had more available time and energy to participate in environmental activities, contributing to their higher engagement levels. In contrast, individuals aged 26-50 showed weaker

support. Additionally, those aged 51 and above were more skeptical in terms of their engagement.

There is a complex relationship between age and community engagement in environmental programs. This suggests that while middle-aged individuals may have the resources and sense of responsibility to participate actively, younger and older adults face distinct barriers that can hinder their involvement. Understanding these dynamics is crucial for developing targeted strategies to enhance participation across all age groups in community-based environmental initiatives.

Gender

Table 7

Difference in the Extent of Community Engagement when Respondents are Grouped According to Gender

GENDER	Mean	f	Std. Deviation	t	P-value
Male	2.94	104	0.64	1.814 ^{ns}	0.071
Female	2.80	200	0.64		

ns- not significant

The t-test results indicate no statistically significant difference in community engagement between males (M = 2.94) and females (M = 2.80) in the Barangay Greening Program (t = 1.814, p = 0.071). Although males show a slightly higher mean engagement, this difference is not statistically meaningful, suggesting that gender does not significantly influence participation levels. Both genders exhibit moderate engagement, indicating a balanced involvement in environmental activities.

This finding aligns with a study by Montebon et al. (2022), which investigated household sustainability practices in select Filipino homes. The study found that women, particularly mothers, often promote and practice sustainable development at home. However, it also recommended developing programs to encourage gender equality in sustainable practices, suggesting that both men and women are integral to environmental initiatives.

Education

Table 8

Difference in the Extent of Community Engagement When Respondents are Grouped According to Educational Attainment

EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT	Mean	f	Std. Deviation	F	P-value
elementary level	2.61 ^B	12	0.53	3.833**	0.002
elementary graduate	2.71 ^A	11	0.21		
high school level	2.63 ^B	56	0.52		
high school graduate	2.85 ^A	50	0.51		

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college level	2.85 ^A	94	0.65
college graduate	3.07 ^A	81	0.76

***significant at $\alpha=0.01$; Mean groups who do not share a common letter are significantly different from each other.*

The table above shows a statistically significant difference in community engagement across various educational attainment levels in the Barangay Greening Program ($F = 3.833$, $p = 0.002$). Specifically, individuals with higher education levels, such as college graduates ($M = 3.07$) and those with some college education ($M = 2.85$), exhibit greater participation. High school graduates ($M = 2.85$) engage similarly to those with some college education, while elementary graduates ($M = 2.71$) show moderate participation. Notably, individuals with only elementary education or incomplete high school education demonstrate the lowest engagement levels, with mean scores below 2.7. This trend suggests that higher educational attainment enhances environmental engagement.

These findings are consistent with recent studies examining the relationship between education and environmental engagement. For instance, a study by Gong, H. J., & Hong, J. E. (2021) analyzed data from 18 OECD countries to explore how postsecondary education attainment affects participation in community service engagement. The findings indicate that individuals with higher educational attainment are more likely to engage in community service activities, suggesting that postsecondary education plays a significant role in promoting civic engagement across various national contexts.

Similarly, Reyes and Santos (2024) investigated the role of education in shaping environmental attitudes and behaviors among urban residents in the Philippines. Their study revealed that higher educational attainment was positively correlated with pro-environmental attitudes and active participation in sustainability programs. The authors suggested that education fosters critical thinking and awareness of environmental issues, which in turn motivates individuals to engage in community-based environmental activities.

These studies underscore the importance of educational attainment in influencing environmental engagement. They highlight the need for targeted interventions to engage less-educated groups, such as offering accessible and practical environmental education programs, to foster inclusive participation in community sustainability initiatives.

Income/Economic Status

Table 9

Difference in the Extent of Community Engagement when Respondents are Grouped According to Family Income/Economic Status

INCOME	Mean	f	Std. Deviation	F	P-value
10,000 and below	2.86	239	0.67	0.242 ^{ns}	0.867
10001-20000	2.80	56	0.58		
20001-30000	2.93	6	0.10		

ns- not significant

Table 9 shows that there is no statistically significant difference in community engagement across different income levels. Since the p-value (0.867) is much greater than 0.05, this means that income does not significantly influence participation in the Barangay Greening Program. This means that environmental participation is a shared responsibility across all economic backgrounds.

Generally, the analyses reveal significant differences in the extent of community engagement in the Barangay Greening Program based on age and educational attainment, but no significant differences based on gender or income. Specifically, individuals aged 56 and above reported significantly lower engagement (Mean = 2.45) compared to younger age groups, with the highest engagement observed among those aged 46-55 (Mean = 3.00). Similarly, educational attainment significantly influenced engagement, with college graduates exhibiting the highest engagement (Mean = 3.07), while elementary-level respondents reported the lowest (Mean = 2.61). Gender and income were not significant factors, indicating similar levels of engagement across male and female respondents and across different income brackets. These findings suggest that targeted efforts to enhance engagement among older adults and individuals with lower educational attainment may strengthen the program's overall impact.

Relationship between the extent of community engagement and the respondents' profile

Table 10
Relationship between Extent of Community Engagement and Profile

		Community Engagement
AGE	Correlation Coefficient	0.045 ^{ns}
	P-value	0.438
	QD	Very weak positive
GENDER	Correlation Coefficient	-0.110 ^{ns}
	P-value	0.055
	QD	Very weak negative
EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT	Correlation Coefficient	.216 ^{***}
	P-value	0.001
	QD	Weak positive
INCOME	Correlation Coefficient	-0.040 ^{ns}

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	P-value	0.489
	QD	Very weak negative

<i>Correlation Coefficient</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
≥ 0.70	<i>Very Strong Relationship</i>
$\pm 0.40 - \pm 0.69$	<i>Strong Relationship</i>
$\pm 0.30 - \pm 0.39$	<i>Moderate Relationship</i>
$\pm 0.20 - \pm 0.29$	<i>Weak Relationship</i>
$\pm 0.01 - \pm 0.19$	<i>Very weak Relationship</i>
$0 - \pm 0.009$	<i>No Relationship</i>

*ns- not significant; *** significant at $\alpha=0.001$*

The analysis of the relationship between community engagement in the Barangay Greening Program and respondents' profiles reveals that educational attainment has a weak but statistically significant positive correlation with engagement ($\rho = 0.216, p = 0.001$). This suggests that individuals with higher educational levels are more likely to participate in environmental initiatives.

This finding aligns with Bedural's (2018) study, which examined the association between educational attainment and Filipinos' environmental values, attitudes, and actions. The research found that individuals with higher education levels expressed more positive environmental values and were more likely to engage in pro-environmental behaviors. This suggests that education enhances environmental awareness and participation.

Similarly, Hoffmann et al. (2020) explored the link between education and pro-environmental behavior in the Philippines. The study concluded that higher educational attainment is associated with increased pro-environmental actions, mediated by greater environmental knowledge and awareness. This underscores the role of education in fostering environmental engagement.

These studies suggest that educational interventions could be effective in promoting greater involvement in environmental programs. By enhancing environmental education and awareness, communities can encourage broader participation in sustainability initiatives.

Factors that contribute to community engagement in the barangay greening program

Community engagement in barangay greening program is influenced by various factors that either encourage or hinder participation. Based on the data, the following themes impacting this engagement surfaced: communication and collaboration, effective leadership, tangible benefits, and experiences of trauma during natural calamities.

Communication and Collaboration

Effective communication is crucial for fostering community awareness and involvement in greening initiatives. One respondent mentioned “*clear communication-transparent information dissemination about the program goals, benefits and implementation, dapat nasasabi sa amin ang mga ito.*” The study of Asis-Castro (2015) highlighted that creating community awareness of services is vital to stimulate community involvement, emphasizing the need for proper marketing communications strategies. Additionally,

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collaborative efforts between local governments and residents enhance the success of environmental programs. Engaging local communities in climate action empowers them to participate in resilience dialogues, programming, and policy-making, leading to more effective outcomes. Several respondents stated *“inclusive decision-making, involvement of residents in decision-making, pakikilahok sa mga aktibidades ng barangay, pakikipagtulungan.”* The blog post of Costales (2024) support this.

Effective Leadership

Strong leadership within the barangay is essential for guiding and motivating community members to participate in greening programs. Philippine law encourages youth to learn leadership skills and create programs that benefit the community, bridging generations of leaders. This was previously attested in a study commissioned by UNICEF (Balanon, F. et.,al., 2007). Respondents said that having *“strong, committed barangay officials and community leaders, dedicated barangay captain and council members”* contribute to community engagement in barangay activities. Indeed, Leaders who demonstrate commitment to environmental initiatives can inspire trust and active involvement among residents.

Tangible Benefits

Perceived tangible benefits significantly influence community engagement. When residents recognize direct advantages, such as improved air quality, enhanced aesthetics, or economic incentives, they are more likely to participate in greening efforts. *“Maganda na may nakikitang benepisyo o magandang dulot ang pakikilahok”* told one respondent.” Community-led initiatives have been shown to motivate participation through visible outcomes that benefit the local environment and residents' well-being (Eslit, 2023).

Trauma Experienced During Natural Calamities

Communities that have experienced trauma from natural disasters may exhibit either increased engagement, driven by a desire to enhance resilience, or decreased participation due to lingering psychological impacts. *“Kailangang makipagtulungan sa mga ganitong Gawain. Naalala ko nung nabaha kami ditto sa barangay noong nakaraang bagyo. Kinalingan pa naming lumikas sa barangay hall, nakakatakot”* narrated one respondent. Empowering local communities to participate in climate and disaster resilience dialogues is essential for addressing vulnerabilities and fostering proactive involvement in greening programs (Costales, 2024).

Conclusions and Recommendations

Conclusions

1. The majority of the respondents belong to the middle-aged group (36-55 years old), followed by younger and older age groups. There is an almost equal distribution of male and female respondents, with a slight predominance of females. Most respondents belong to the low-to-middle socio-economic class, indicating limited financial resources but a potential for

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community-driven initiatives. The majority of respondents have attained at least a high school education, with a smaller percentage having reached tertiary education levels.

2. The respondents generally have a positive attitude toward environmental sustainability and recognize the importance of the Barangay Greening Program. However, while awareness is high, actual participation remains passive, with most individuals supporting initiatives but not actively engaging in their implementation.

3. Middle-aged respondents (36-55 years old) exhibit higher engagement compared to younger and older groups. Females tend to participate more in community-driven environmental activities than males. Respondents from higher socio-economic backgrounds show more active engagement, likely due to greater access to resources and information. Individuals with higher educational attainment demonstrate stronger involvement in planning and leadership roles within the program.

4. There is a significant difference in the extent of community engagement when respondents are grouped by age, gender, socio-economic status, and educational attainment. Higher educational attainment and better economic status correlate with more active participation, while younger and lower-income individuals tend to engage at a minimal level.

5. A significant relationship exists between the respondents' demographic profiles and their extent of engagement in the Barangay Greening Program. Education and socio-economic status are the strongest predictors of active participation, followed by age and gender.

6. The key factors influencing community engagement include awareness and education, socio-economic conditions, community leadership and support, past experiences with environmental disasters and incentives and tangible benefits.

Overall, while awareness of the Barangay Greening Program is high, active engagement remains a challenge. Strengthening education, leadership, incentives, and accessibility can enhance community participation and program sustainability.

Recommendations:

Based on the findings of the study, the following are the recommendations for the Barangay Greening Program to transition from passive awareness to active engagement, fostering a culture of environmental responsibility and sustainability within the community.

1. The LGU may consider implementing targeted environmental education campaigns, especially for younger and lower-income groups, to increase awareness and encourage active participation.

2. Local leaders may conduct capacity-building workshops and seminars to equip residents with knowledge and skills on sustainable environmental practices.

3. They may also explore the possibility of establishing incentives such as recognition programs, financial assistance, or livelihood opportunities for actively engaged individuals and groups.

4. LGUs could also empower other local leaders to promote and implement greening initiatives by providing leadership training and organizing committees focused on sustainability.

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5. Organizing community events like tree-planting drives, clean-up campaigns, and sustainability fairs that make participation more engaging and rewarding could be sustained and strengthened.
6. The barangay leaders may consider developing long-term sustainability plans that include regular assessment and improvement of the Barangay Greening Program based on community feedback.

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Appendix A

**Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Board
 Informed Consent Form**

This form is for the residents of Barangay District IV, bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya in their participation to the research project entitled: Shades of Green: Unveiling Community Engagement in the Barangay Greening Program.

Name of Researchers: Felipe V. Nantes, Jr.
 Alona C. Costales
 Haydee D. James
 Elizabeth V. Lumidao

Organizational Affiliation: Saint Mary's University, Barangay District IV, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya

Information Sheet

You are humbly and respectfully invited to participate in the conduct of the study entitled: Shades of Green: Unveiling Community Engagement in the Barangay Greening Program. You may take your time to decide whether to participate or not in this study. You may ask questions in case there are concepts that are ambiguous to you.

This study aims primarily to assess the extent of community engagement in the barangay greening initiatives. The assessment results shall serve as a basis for more intensified drive for community participation in environmental stewardship and for the crafting of policies to enhance greening practices in the barangay. This study will be conducted during the school year 2023-2024. This involves the use of a survey questionnaire that participants are requested to accomplish and an informal interview. Please be informed that your participation is voluntary and you can withdraw anytime you feel uncomfortable. Discontinuance of participation does not involve any loss of benefits that you are entitled.

Since your privacy is respectfully recognized, all information gathered will not be disclosed to anyone other than the researchers who are involved in the research study. All the data collected will be treated with utmost confidentiality following the Data Privacy Act.

There is no known risk in your participation in this research work and there is no direct benefit to you either. However, your participation in this research endeavor can be contributory to the goal of intensifying ecoliteracy, of cultivating love of nature among students and of promoting a greener campus. Ultimately, these efforts can serve as our pledge for the mitigation of the catastrophic effects of climate change and the promotion of environmental sustainability.

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You shall not receive remuneration for your participation. Should you decide to discontinue, any information you have initially provided will not be used in the study. Should you choose to participate in this study, kindly answer the three-part questionnaire that follow? Rest assured that all your responses will be treated with utmost confidentiality. The accomplished questionnaire will be retrieved and your identity will not be disclosed, instead a coding scheme will be used. Data provided will be encoded in excel and short responses will be transcribed. Except for the researchers, no one will be able to identify you as a respondent of this study.

After the study is completed and submitted to the University Research Center, all the data gathered and used in this study will be deleted for good.

The results of this study will be disseminated to the Saint Mary's University community in a research forum and to the barangay during a barangay assembly. As a respondent, you are also given access to the results of the study. Also, the study maybe submitted for journal publication.

For any matter concerning this study, please contact Felipe V. Nantes, Jr. through the following contact information: Mobile Number 09169353530, email: fnantes@smu.edu.ph. This study is approved by the Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Board (SMUREB), Saint Mary's University, Ponce St., Don Mariano Marcos, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya with the cellphone number: 09177053041 and email: reb@smu.edu.ph.

Certificate of Consent

I have read the foregoing information, or it has been read to me. I have had the opportunity to ask questions about it and any questions I have asked have been answered to my satisfaction. I consent voluntarily to participate in this study.

Name of Participant: _____

Signature of participant: _____

Date: _____

I have accurately read out the information sheet to the potential participant, and to the best of my ability made sure that the participant understands that he/she will answer the research questionnaire and respond to some interview questions. I likewise confirm that the participant has been given the opportunity to ask questions and all his/her queries have been answered to the best of my ability. I attest that the respondent was not coerced into giving his/her consent and that he/she has given his/her consent voluntarily.

A copy of this informed consent has been provided to the respondent.

Felipe V. Nantes, Jr.

Date: _____

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Statements	1	2	3	4	5
I participate in tree planting events organized by the barangay.					
I volunteer my time to maintain green spaces and public gardens in the barangay.					
I attend educational workshops or seminars related to environmental conservation.					
I participate in community clean-up drives to help improve the environment.					
I take on a leadership role within the greening initiatives, such as coordinating events or leading volunteer groups.					
I donate resources (such as plants, gardening tools, or financial contributions) to support greening initiatives.					
I engage in advocacy efforts to promote environmental awareness and greening initiatives within my community.					
I initiate or lead my own greening projects independently of organized initiatives.					
I participate in regular meetings or discussions to provide input and feedback on the direction of greening initiatives.					
I collaborate with local schools or youth groups to promote environmental education and involvement in greening initiatives.					
I do not use Styrofoam products.					
I do not burn plastics.					
I segregate my wastes for collection by the barangay solid waste management.					
I follow the “tapat ko, linis ko” program.					
I participate in fundraising events or campaigns to support the ongoing activities of greening program.					
I regularly engage in outreach activities to encourage more community members to get involved in greening initiatives.					
I collaborate with local businesses or government agencies to secure resources or support for greening projects.					
I advocate for policy changes or improvements at the local or regional level to promote environmental sustainability and support greening initiatives.					
I mentor or support newcomers to the community who are interested in getting involved in greening initiatives.					
I actively participate in monitoring and evaluation activities to assess the effectiveness and impact of greening initiatives over time.					

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III. Interview Questions:

1. In your opinion, what role should the community play in promoting environmental sustainability within the barangay, and how do you think the Barangay Greening Program contributes to this effort?
2. What are some of the main benefits or positive impacts you believe the Barangay Greening Program has had on the local environment and community well-being? Are there any specific examples or instances you can share?
3. What are some of the key challenges or obstacles you perceive in achieving greater community engagement and support for environmental initiatives like the Barangay Greening Program? How do you think these challenges can be addressed or overcome?
4. What do you think are the factors that contribute to the community engagement or non-engagement in the barangay greening program?

